

IMPROVEMENT AND DEVELOPMENT OF RURAL CONDITIONS

Otabek UmarovZulfikarovich

Tashkent University of Architecture and Construction, senior
teacher

<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-2913-4378> bekolmas@mail.ru

Annotation: The reconstruction of the village is impossible without changing the traditional way of life of the rural population, which is understood as a system of activities carried out by the population, determined by the external environment and the specific characteristics of the rural population. The main direction of improving labor in social production will be the further acceleration of the industrialization of agriculture.

In modern conditions, personal subsidiary farming is an objective necessity, as it serves as one of the sources of life support. The ability to manage one's own household is an important advantage of rural life, allowing even large, numerous families to maintain sufficient material well-being at very low wages in social production. The emergence of new complex techniques that replace manual labor with machine labor in the countryside requires special knowledge.

Key words: agriculture, labor, enterprise, professional, activity, farmer, education, animal husbandry, pasture, mechanization.

Almost half of the population of Uzbekistan lives in villages, the development of the country and the prosperity of the people depends on the future of the village. The head of our state paid special attention to the protection of the interests of the middle class of the population - owners, entrepreneurs, and businessmen - the new ownership relations that are forming in the village.

The share of peasant farms in the gross agricultural product is 63.7 percent (62.9 percent in January-December 2020), farms 34.1 percent (35.0 percent), agricultural enterprises 2.2 percent (2.1 percent).

According to statistics, as of October 1, 2010. 218,000 farms worked in Uzbekistan. 1.7 million people worked on average of 27 hectares each. There were about 4.6 million peasant farms.

In recent years, the main productive force of Uzbekistan's agriculture has been farmers and peasant farms. According to statistics, by the end of 9 months, 65 percent of the gross agricultural product in Uzbekistan is accounted for by farmers. The share of farmers is 33.1%, and the rest belongs to companies.

In our country, as in previous years, the State program on the development of industrial production and construction in the countryside, the establishment of compact processing enterprises, and the improvement of the service sector will be adopted.

Rural reconstruction is impossible without changing the traditional way of life of the rural population, which is understood as a system of activities carried out by the population determined by the external environment and the specific characteristics of the rural population. Practice and scientific studies show that the rural lifestyle includes the following main types of activities: work in social production, work in personal auxiliary farms, household, activities related to education and skills, cultural activities for recreation, social work.

Labor in social production. Satisfied needs in the field of work are usually expressed by the level of job satisfaction and the presence (absence) of the opportunity to change the enterprise, workplace, profession. Dissatisfaction with work is mainly related to its conditions and to a lesser extent to its content. The working conditions of rural workers in Uzbekistan are currently difficult - people are forced to work most of the time in the open air, in unfavorable conditions; village constructions of farm machines do not always take into account the climatic features of the republic and are inconvenient; conditions are created for the repair of equipment away from all farms; in many cases, the lack of comfortable and poorly

equipped production areas (field camps, repair workshops, livestock farms, etc.) does not allow for effective organization of workers' work and rest.

A characteristic feature of the content of rural labor in the republic is the superiority of physical labor over mental labor. According to sociological studies conducted in Fergana, Jizzakh and Kashkadarya regions, more than 90 percent of rural residents are mainly engaged in manual labor. Another feature is the large number of unprofessional workers. On the one hand, there are many jobs that do not require professional work, and on the other hand, there are still many workers who do not have special education. In addition, this applies to women more than men. About 25 percent of the workers have education in the amount of courses or vocational schools, which in the countryside are often considered sufficient to carry out skilled, in particular, mechanization work. The next characteristic is often single-shift work, which actually extends to most of the daylight hours; its seasonality associated with the specific characteristics of agricultural production (traffic in summer and autumn and excess free time in winter); not using weekends and working holidays (from not fulfilling the mandatory minimum of working days to the inability to leave one's home). However, in general, the attitude of rural workers to their work remains positive.

The main direction of improvement of labor in social production will be further acceleration of industrialization of agriculture. Its basis is to solve not only production, but also social problems of the village. Reconstruction, beautification of production sites, agricultural complexes, corporate technical service and repair of agricultural machinery (adapted to hot climate conditions), simplification of work mode, elimination of seasonality, mechanization and automation of work, production measures should be developed to increase the share of output, skilled workers.

Labor in private farming. In today's conditions, a personal auxiliary economy is an objective necessity, as it serves as one of the sources of the livelihood

fund. It satisfies the economic needs of families, serves as an additional source of income obtained by selling products and (or) saving money to buy them in the trade network. The ability to manage one's own household is an important advantage of rural life, allowing even large, numerous families to maintain sufficient material well-being with very low wages in social production.

In Uzbekistan, the role of private auxiliary farms is the largest in the production of vegetables, potatoes, livestock products. Unlike other countries of the CIS, the weight of private auxiliary farms in the production of livestock products in the republic is slightly larger. Animal husbandry accounts for the main part of labor costs (up to 74%). The peculiarity of work in personal auxiliary farms is that it is multifaceted, it requires various tools and equipment, as well as relevant knowledge and skills. At the same time, this work is still poorly mechanized - the main share is manual labor. Therefore, it is distinguished by its long duration, especially in rural women. Lack of pasture, fodder, pasture irrigation water aggravates this situation and makes it difficult to run private auxiliary farms.

Thus, there is a conflict between the variety of urgent needs of the rural population, which are satisfied in the field of personal auxiliary economy, the material base of the farm and the amount of labor, energy and funds required for its establishment and maintenance. These contradictions can be resolved primarily by helping farmers, farmers, private auxiliary farms (cooperation with private auxiliary farms, establishing a solid system of irrigation water supply, small-scale mechanization, concentrated feed, can be eliminated by providing fodder, labor costs, etc.). Private estates, workshops, private estates services will be developed on the basis of a family contract.

As a result of the consistent implementation of these measures, the work in the private auxiliary economy changes its content: material needs must gradually be replaced by psychological needs, economic needs must be replaced by pleasure training. All this increases the free time budget, attracting additional resources to

social production allows, creates conditions for the harmonious improvement of the individual. This process is accompanied by a consistent change in the planning structure of settlements in the direction of a gradual reduction in the size of estates, their production structure, creation of auxiliary crafts - private estates, workshops, family estates or rental contracts.

Household activities. The characteristics of the household extinguish many different occupations according to their social role. These are housing, nutrition, health care, sanitation, care for things (furniture, clothes, shoes), consumption of cultural and household services (buying food, occupations related to cleaning things, washing clothes, etc.).

One of the important needs of everyday life is related to housing. As a rule, preference is given to a separate, private house. People are motivated by the fact that it provides family independence, a sense of ownership, independence from the workplace, the convenience of running a personal assistant farm, peace and tranquility, familiarity, and does not require constant worry about paying for an apartment. Most of the dwellings in the village are deprived of communal facilities. Characteristic - lack of gas, water supply, central heating, sewerage, hot water supply. The low level of improvement forces rural people to do household chores that most urbanites do not have at all. The abundance of labor-intensive domestic work is also related to the low mechanization of the main types of domestic work. Although the supply of some household appliances is growing rapidly, the existing electrical household appliances cannot meet all the needs of the rural population or even their basic household needs. Labor-intensive and heavy work, such as fetching water, preparing firewood, preparing fodder for livestock, is performed without any technical means. Now the villagers are in dire need of water supply, sewage, firewood, feed preparation, animal care, vegetable and fruit harvesting and processing machinery.

Another set of daily problems is related to meeting the needs of personal care and household items (linen, washing and cleaning clothes, repairing household appliances, nutrition, body hygiene, aesthetic co 'appearance'). The main part of the listed works is carried out today in the village family. The organization of life within the family, which is traditional for the village, often turns out to be stronger than the offer developed from the life service. Therefore, the need for household services is still underdeveloped. Sociological research data show that one of the clear reasons why villagers do not work in public production is household employment (47.7% of respondents in Pakhtaabad villages of Andijan region - a total of 96.5 thousand people). 74% of them (70% of men and 75% of women) expressed their desire to participate in the field of social production, if appropriate conditions were created for them.

Changing the traditional system of rural life is carried out through the rapid development of the provision of household services, which surpasses the stereotype of household needs in the village. Here, we will not ignore the commissioning of public service facilities. In addition to housing construction, the creation of a regional service system plays an important role. Here is the purchase of local engineering equipment (heating, water supply, sewage), as well as gasification, telephony, mechanized household appliances and equipment.

Educational activities. Education and training of the working-age population is important for the village, firstly, there is a category of workers whose education level is lower than the set requirements due to the nature of work; secondly, there are types of work that require special knowledge, but are not provided with appropriate workers. Both tasks are partially solved by increasing the education of workers, that is, by incorporating education into their lifestyle. As noted above, the weak manifestation of the need for education in the countryside is due to the insufficient introduction of mechanization and automation to rural labor and, as a result, the predominance of a large share of manual labor. At the same time, the

main reasons are the remoteness of rural workers from their places of residence and work and the poor transport connection of educational institutions (universities, technical schools). Weak manifestation of the need for education, as well as many difficulties in rural life (poor housing, heavy work, lack of free time due to personal auxiliary farming, etc.) It can be explained by the fact that the problems of rural workers were put forward, in the background, as if they were crushed by more urgent and pressing issues. Hence, the emergence of rural traditions - the unsuitability of combining work with study for a large part of the rural population.

The improvement of educational activities will be connected, first of all, with the rapid pace of industrialization of agricultural production. The emergence of new complex techniques that replace manual labor with machine labor in the countryside requires special knowledge.

New occupations related to the maintenance and management of new equipment and automated systems will emerge. Only general and secondary special education will not be enough - people will have to increase their level of education. It is important to expand the network of rural lyceums, colleges, departments of higher educational institutions, research institutes in the villages, and improve the transport connection between the village and the city. By mechanizing manual labor, freeing up people's time for studying helps to solve the problem of the quality of training of specialists.

Rest. In the field of recreation, it mainly satisfies three types of needs: restoration of psychophysiological balance, self-expression, and spiritual consumption. Currently, the category of "free time" in relation to the village is filled with meaning, far from a simple concept. Here we keep in mind the great role of labor professions that perform leisure functions (housework, home repair, etc.) and preserve traditional free time for the village.

The peculiarity of spending free time in the countryside is, first of all, less diversity of cultural and educational activities, the absence of some activities that

are common in the city (lecture halls, museums, sightseeing) visiting exhibitions, working in thematic clubs, etc.); secondly, to a lesser extent, the development of many professions.

Villagers usually spend their free time doing housework, watching TV, etc. There is very little time spent on active recreation (sports, amateur performances, visiting libraries, etc.). There is not enough free time during the field work season (one-shift work during the day, manual labor - as a result of which fatigue is felt in the evening), there is a lot of free time in winter. However, the narrowness of rural cultural institutions, insufficient material and technical base and types of services, lack of comfortable conditions, lack of training of cultural workers to a low level of knowledge do not ensure full recreation. If we add to this the fact that a lot of time and effort is spent on private auxiliary farms, the work of pre-school educational institutions is not high enough, and the general education level of the population is low, why the need for cultural expenses of the rural population is weakly expressed? we can understand. their free time.

It turns out that the higher the dissatisfaction with cultural life, the higher the level of people's skills and general education. This problem is solved by mechanizing manual labor, switching to a two-shift work mode, eliminating seasonality, contributing to the emergence of free time.

Rapid formation of the system of cultural and household services in villages, construction of state institutions, raising the general educational and cultural level of the population should help to form the need for cultural communication, public events, etc. The construction of pre-school education and sports facilities, the provision of engineering communications to settlements will have a positive effect on improving the lifestyle of rural residents.

So, the traditional lifestyle of the rural population of Uzbekistan has its own characteristics. Consistent development of agro-industry integration, new production, formation of economic and social relations have a consistent positive

effect on changing the traditional lifestyle of the village. The presented directions of its change consistently lead to the formation of new social values, ways of thinking, which directly affect the gradual disappearance of the border between the city and the countryside from a socio-economic point of view.

Proper consideration of the social processes taking place in the village will help to solve the problem of its transformation.

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